

TRPV-Dependent Gain Control of Mechanical Amplification in an Ear

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Abstract. By amplifying sound-induced vibrations in an intensity- and frequency specific manner, ears can sharpen their resonant mechanics. Ears boost their mechanical input with motile auditory receptors. In *Drosophila*, this mechanical amplification is controlled by heteromeric TRPV channels formed by Nanchung (Nan) and Inactive (Iav) (Nan-Iav).

Nan-Iav promote calcium entry into auditory receptors and can be activated *in vitro* by nicotinamide (NAM), an intermediate metabolite of the NAD-salvage pathway. We identify NAM as a direct, endogenous ligand of these TRPV channels, regulating their activity *in vivo*, in auditory receptors, and, thus, the mechanical amplification gain in the ear. NAM is enzymatically removed by nicotinamidase (Naam), allowing for a regulation of TRPV activity. Both, nicotinamidase and TRPV activity are matched to each other, with calcium modulating the activity of nicotinamidase by binding to its EF-hand motifs.

Thus, we can establish *in vivo* ligand-gating of TRPV channels by a cell-autonomous mechanism that allows to couple auditory mechanics to the metabolic state of the auditory receptors. Here, NAM-activated TRPV channels result in calcium-influx that subsequently enhances NAM turnover, providing a molecular feedback loop that allows to adjust the mechanical feedback gain by regulating auditory receptor motility.

INTRODUCTION

The basic principle of cochlear amplification, akin to that found in human hearing, is also utilized by the hearing organs of insects, such as *Drosophila melanogaster*. Housed in the second antennal segment (Johnston's Organ [JO]), the JO-neurons are required for the mechano-electrical transduction of deflections of the antenna by sound, gravity or wind. The cilia of auditory JO-neurons not only transduce mechanical stimuli but are also motile. Mathematically, the antennal oscillations can be described using a simple harmonic oscillator [1].

This auditory receptor motility allows for positive mechanical feedback to improve the overall sensitivity of the ear to sound. By adjusting the amount of energy spend on active oscillations, it is possible to modulate the sensitivity and frequency tuning. The gain control of mechanical amplification relies on a negative feedback loop that requires the heteromeric TRPV1 channel Nanchung-Inactive (Nan-Iav). The absence of either TRPV1 ion channel results in the loss of neuronal auditory responses [2]. However, counterintuitively, the loss of Iav or Nan is accompanied by hyperamplification [3].

Nan-Iav can be activated in chordotonal neurons in *Drosophila* larvae by nicotinamide (NAM), which subsequently leads to increased intra-cellular Ca^{2+} levels [4]. Interestingly, the NAM hydrolysing enzyme nicotinamidase is highly expressed in the Johnston's Organ and is regulated age-dependently [5]. Thus, we expected a loss in the amplification and neuronal responses of auditory neurons in nicotinamidase knockout mutant flies.

Studying enzymes involved in Nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide (NAD) metabolism *in vivo* is challenging, as most knockouts result in lethality (i.e. NMNAT [6]), or, like sirtuins, have multiple isoforms that can compensate for the loss of a particular isoform [7]. Here, we characterized a viable knockout line of the *Drosophila* nicotinamidase (*DmNaam*).

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METHODS

Antennal Free Fluctuations

The fly stocks used in this study and their respective origins are: *Mi{MIC}Naam^{MI12364}* aka Naam-KO (BDSC #58512), its genetically matched control *w¹¹¹⁸* (BDSC #3605) and *iav¹* aka iav-KO (Gong et al., 2004), *nan^{26a}* aka TRPV-KO (BDSC: #24902), *w¹¹¹⁸/w¹¹¹⁸;nSyb-LexA/CyO;LexAop-GCaMP6m/TM6C* aka GCaMP6 (combined stock of BDSC #52237 and BDSC #44275). Flies were tested two to five days post-eclosure. Flies were maintained and experiments were performed in accordance with German federal regulations (license Gen.Az 501.40611/0166/501).

Unconstrained movements of the arista are driven by the thermal motion and active motion of the JO neurons. To measure these free fluctuations, flies were completely immobilized except for the antenna being measured. The displacements of the free antenna were measured using a Polytec PSV-400 scanning laser Doppler vibrometer equipped with a DD-500 displacement decoder. The velocity amplitudes were fast Fourier-transformed (FFT) to generate a frequency spectrum for the antenna vibration velocity in the range of 100-1500 Hz. The velocity amplitudes were then converted into displacement amplitudes and squared to obtain the power spectral density (PSD) [1, 8]. The PSD can then be fitted with a harmonic oscillator, with the peak being the individual best frequency (IBF, the eigenfrequency of the oscillator) and dimensionless tuning parameter Q, which describes the frequency selectivity. The total energy in kBT of the oscillator was calculated from the fit parameters as described previously [1, 8].

Calcium Imaging

Calcium responses upon nicotinamide (NAM) feeding were measured in the JO. Measurements were performed using a Zeiss Axio Examiner.D1 microscope (Carl Zeiss AG, Oberkochen, Germany) with an Orca Flash 4.0 camera (Hamamatsu Orca Flash 4.0 V2, C11440-22CU, Hamamatsu Photonics K.K., Hamamatsu, Japan, Filter BP470/40 nm, BP525/50 nm). Flies were immobilized and the JO was imaged from the top through a coverslip (Zeiss Objective W "Plan-Apochromat" 40x/1.0 DIC M27). As calcium indicator, the genetically encoded GCaMP6m [9] was pan-neuronally expressed (neuronal-synaptobrevin promoter (nSyb-LexA)) with the LexA-LexAop binary expression system [10].

The head, base of the antenna, and thorax of flies (pre-starved on H₂O for 12h prior experiment) were glued to a microscope coverslip up-side-down using transparent UV-hardening glue. Flies were fed 10mM NAM (Sigma-Aldrich, Munich, Germany, #72340) in 1% Sucrose (Merck KGaA, Darmstadt, Germany, #57-50-1) and recorded for three hours. Images were taken every 1–10 min, while exposure to fluorescent light was kept to a minimum by illuminating the JO only during the image acquisition.

Enzymatic Activity

Drosophila nicotinamidase was cloned from extracted RNA, via generated cDNA, and finally placed into a UAS-attB-vector, where it was fused to GFP. The Naam::GFP fusion protein was recombinantly expressed in *Drosophila* S2-cells and purified using GFP selector agarose (NanoTag, Göttingen, Germany, #N0310). Enzymatic activity was measured using an adapted PNC1 (*C.elegans* Naam) activity-assay (OPT-assay) [11] that detects free NH₄⁺. Additionally iso-thermal calorimetry [12] was used to quantitatively determine binding affinities, enthalpy changes during NAM hydrolysis by nicotinamidase. Following the heat exchange per time one can now calculate the reaction rate and subsequently allows the calculation of enzymatic activity.

FIGURE 1. Frequency tuning and mechanical amplification of the *Drosophila* ear. **a)** Upon feeding with 10mM nicotinamide (NAM) the flies lose their sharp tuning (Q) and the individual best frequency (IBF) of the oscillations shifts towards higher frequencies. This is accompanied by a loss of mechanical amplification as the flies invest less energy (E) in the active oscillations. **b)** Loss of *DmTRPV1* (*iav-KO*) leads to hyper-amplification and sharp tuning, together with a sensitivity shift towards lower frequencies. A knockout of the TRPV1-agonist NAM-degrading enzyme nicotinamidase (*Naam-KO*) results in decreased mechanical amplification, and reduced frequency selectivity.

RESULTS

NAM Concentration Controls Gain

In a first experiment we checked, if hearing of *wildtype* control flies depends on NAM levels in JO-neurons. We measured the free fluctuations of a fly, fed 10mM NAM and monitored the auditory receptors for the next 180min (Fig.1a). The sharp tuning at ~260Hz and the active energy contributions from the auditory receptors were transiently lost (-7.19 κBT) after feeding with NAM. The energy dropped by ~80% and the antenna lost its sharp tuning within 20min. This was accompanied by a shift of the individual best frequency to ~380Hz. After ~2h, hearing mostly recovered. Thus, there is a strong correlation between systemic NAM levels and a reduced gain of mechanical amplification in *Drosophila* ear.

Compared to controls, *iav-KO* flies exhibited a 16 times sharper tuning and showed a slight shift of the individual best frequency by ~50Hz towards a lower frequency (Fig.1b). Without the negative feedback loop that limits the energy of the antennal motions in controls, *iav-KO* flies spend 17 times more energy on motility (~215 κBT). Consistent with a loss of gain control in TRPV-KO flies, loss of the NAM degrading enzyme nicotinamidase resulted in strongly reduced active motility of the antenna (Fig.1b). With a reduction of energy of the oscillation by 85%, the ear's tuning became broader and the individual best frequency shifted to ~630Hz (Fig.1b). Thus, *Naam-KO* flies exhibit hearing loss.

NAM Modulates Intra-cellular Ca^{2+} Levels of JO-neurons

Measurements of the antennal free fluctuations indicated that NAM effects commence within 5-20min after ingestion. Therefore, we wanted to check if the slow recovery coincided with acute changes in the intra-cellular Ca^{2+} levels and, if so, if these changes depend on the activation of *DmTRPV1* by NAM. Much like larval chordotonal cells [4], elevating NAM levels increased cytoplasmic Ca^{2+} levels in JO neurons. (Fig.2a). Consistent with effects on the antennal mechanics, Ca^{2+} levels started to increase within 8-15min after one food bout with 10mM NAM. Usually, Ca^{2+} levels peaked between 30-60min before slowly lowering towards baseline (Fig.2a). However, a knockout of TRPV1 did not lead to significant changes in Ca^{2+} levels upon NAM exposure (Fig.2a). Thus, the modulating effects of NAM result from the Nan-Iav activation by NAM in a dose-dependent manner.

FIGURE 2. Effect of Nicotinamide (NAM) on Ca^{2+}_i levels and activities of nicotinamidase and TRPV1 at different NAM concentrations a) Ca^{2+} influx into auditory neurons after feeding of NAM. b) Normalized activities for TRPV activation (blue, parameters from [4]) and Nicotinamidase (Naam) [ITC] (black), OPT (red, dashed), KG (parameters from [13], teal, dotted)

Nicotinamidase Activity is Fine-tuned to the Dynamic Range of *Dm*TRPV1 Gating by NAM and Depends on Cytoplasmic Ca^{2+} Concentration

Next, we were interested in the regulation of NAM and, thus, the activity of the TRPV channels. For this we recombinantly expressed and purified nicotinamidase and measured the catalytic activity on NAM, then compared it to literature data [4] on the NAM-induced activity of *Dm*TRPV1 (Fig.2b). Starting with coupled enzymatic assays that detect the NAM hydrolysis by-product NH_3^+ , we could see similar K_M values in our used OPT-assay ($K_M = 173\mu\text{M}$) and published data [13] ($K_M = 193\mu\text{M}$) (Fig.2b). This would place Nicotinamidase's activity range to NAM concentrations that would allow a modulation *Dm*TRPV1 at maximum open probability. However, when we measured the enzymatic activity directly, with much more sensitive ITC, Nicotinamidase activity ($K_M = 11.2\mu\text{M}$, $k_{cat} = 17.9\text{s}^{-1}$) set in at lower nicotinamide levels than NAN-IAV activity ($P_{0.5} = 14.4\mu\text{M}$) (Fig. 2b). Thus, *in vivo* NAM levels seem to be fine-adjusted by nicotinamidase that allows for a minuscule modulation of *Dm*TRPV1 activity.

DISCUSSION

Our data from *in vivo* and *in vitro* experiments indicate a tight coupling of the activity of *Dm*TRPV1 and the agonist removing enzyme nicotinamidase (*Dm*Naam). Gain control of the *Dm* ear is thus dependent on the acute concentration of the NAD-salvage pathway intermediate metabolite NAM.

Interestingly, during metazoan evolution, nicotinamidase acquired two N-terminally located EF-hand motifs that would allow for a possible regulation of the enzyme's activity by local Ca^{2+} levels. Indeed, preliminary data from ITC experiments provide evidence for increased activity of *Dm*nicotinamidase at higher Ca^{2+} levels. Moreover, similarly to calmodulin that can bind to TRPV1 channels [14], *Dm*nicotinamidase EF-Hands might allow for a localization to the same binding site that is in close proximity to the TRPV1 binding site for NAM, and thus would enable a fast removal of the TRPV1 agonist.

CONCLUSION

In summary, JO neurons rely on activated TRPV1 channels to modulate mechanical amplification of hearing. Here we show that NAM qualifies as an endogenous agonist of TRPV1 *in vivo*. This is accompanied by a tight regulation of the NAM levels in the cell as chordotonal cells exhibit a notably high expression of nicotinamidase, which converts NAM into Nicotinic acid (vitamin B3) that subsequently can be used for NAD synthesis. This would allow for a mechanism that couples the energy state of the cell to the modulation of mechanical amplification (Fig.3)

During metabolic states of high ATP-synthesis, most of the NAD^+ exists only in protonated form (NADH/H^+) or

FIGURE 3. Schematic of feedback loop of NAM regulating Gain/Amplification in the *Drosophila* ear via Nan-Iav. Nicotinamidase (=Naam); agonist NAM (Nicotinamide)

as NADPH. As a result, NAD-consumers like PARPs (reviewed in [15]) or sirtuins (reviewed in [16]) will not generate NAM. Hence, Nan-Iav is not stimulated and the JO-neurons utilize energy to promote strong mechanical amplification.

However, if the JO neurons cannot produce much energy, NAD levels rise and lead to increased metabolization into NAM that can activate Nan-Iav. Increased, Ca^{2+} levels lead to reduced mechanical amplification and concomitantly, to elevated nicotinamidase activity to remove the agonist NAM.

Thus, the JO-neurons can autonomously adjust their motility and energy expenditure, depending on their metabolic state.

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COMMENTS AND DISCUSSION

[Catalina, Velez-Ortega]: Very interesting data! We love the conclusion cartoon at the end of the paper. Here are some comments/questions that we had:

1. For experiment in Figure 1a, would the response change after feeding with just 1% sucrose control (i.e. without NAM)?
2. Similarly, would feeding NAM (in sucrose) to *Iav*-KO (TRPV1 KO) flies produce any changes to their tuning curves?
3. We wonder whether NAM could activate a negative feedback mechanism independent from its action on TRPV1.
4. We are not entirely sure how the TRPV1 activity was obtained to generate Figure 2b. Could you perhaps expand in the methods section?
5. We would love to see the preliminary data showing increased nicotinamidase activity at higher calcium levels in the paper.

[Philip, Hehlert]: Thank you for the nice comments. Here a point by point response:

1. Of course flies were pre-starved for this experiment to ensure food-intake and thus uptake of our NAM spiked sucrose solution. Compared to Fig 1 b one can already see slightly lower Energy of the system when measuring the starved flies. After feeding with sole sucrose solution we expect a slightly higher Energy, thus the opposite effect to the NAM treatment. We will perform this control experiment in the near future.
2. Feeding NAM to TRPV-KO (flies with *iav*[1] allele) only leads to a minor non-significant increase in the Energy of the system (slightly higher amplitudes without altering IBF). Due to space constrictions this data has not been shown. Potentially the ingested NAM will be metabolized that allows for overall more efficient energy production of the JONs and might explain this small effect.
3. We have data on this question that has not been presented due to space limitations. We also tested a double knockout of nicotinamidase and *Dm*TRPV1 and still could observe the hyper-amplification. Your question is also the reason why Ca²⁺ Imaging was performed in *Dm*TRPV1-KO flies. It appears that there is still residual response to feeding NAM. However feeding NAM to *Dm*TRPV1-KO in these excess amounts should then result in an observable reduction in Energy, which we cannot observe.
4. I expanded the method section slightly to clarify what exactly was measured by the respective assays. Due to space limitations a detailed description of measurements and calculations was omitted but will be available upon request. The most sensitive and direct measurement is the ITC as we follow directly the thermodynamics during hydrolysis.
5. The preliminary data was shown on the poster and is currently repeated for final publication.

[Thomas, Effertz]: Thank you for the interesting paper. All in all an interesting story and I am looking forward to hearing more about it in the future.

1. Before getting into the details, I would suggest a different abbreviation for the nicotinamidase. Naam is too confusingly similar to NAM and does not follow the same abbreviation rules. Maybe NAMase or NAMam would be more appropriate. Else, a discussion at the poster might get confusing. . . fast. Maybe with a sentence like “While usually abbreviated Naam, we chose to use NAMase to reduce confusing the enzyme with its substrate.”
2. Regarding the effect on the free fluctuations while feeding NAM, did you also look at earlier time points than 20 minutes and are there any estimates on how fast the animals can absorb NAM from a food source?
3. Regarding Ca²⁺ imaging, it is surprising to see in Figure 2a a counter directional behaviour for ctrl and TRPV-KO animals at the beginning of the experiment. Did you also perform measurement points before feeding NAM to the animals? These would be informative regarding possible bleaching or motion artifacts.
4. Playing devils advocate for a second, how can you be sure that the observed effects are due to a direct interaction between NAM and nan/iav and not just a reduction in systemic energy levels that lead to a reduced amplification by JO neurons? The same could be said for the NAMase knockout animals, where possible a higher concentration of NAM could just affect systemic energy levels. Could maybe behavioural experiments that for example look at locomotion be telling regarding general energy levels vs a local effect in only JO neurons?
5. IBF, individual best frequency should be used more consistently, you also use eigenfrequency or best frequency intermittently.

[Philip, Hehlert]: Thank you for the constructive feedback. Here a point by point response:

1. I agree that the similar naming scheme can create confusion. Several publications are available that use "Naam" as abbreviation. Also, the *Dm*-database www.flybase.org lists Naam as gene symbol and official abbreviation. Thus, I decided to stay with this establish naming convention and avoid the abbreviation in the text completely and clarify it in the figure legend.
2. Based from literature and personal experiments the passing time of food (from ingestion to defecation is around 20min) and food usually arrives in the midgut after around 10min. We allowed for maximally two food bouts and started the experiment with the removal of the capillary with the liquid food. Individual flies showed faster responses of decreasing amplification but varied strongly between animals. Earliest changes could be detected after around 8min. For a robust maximal effect on the amplification reduction we opted for 20min. A direct systemic administration of 10mM NAM in 1xPBS into the hemolymph resulted in decreased amplification within 1-2min but the effect was unreliable due to variable application. As ingestion works as well we opted for the less invasive option.
3. In the meantime we improved the setup so that the animal doesn't have to be moved to the microscope after the feeding. This reduces potential effects from positional changes of the antenna and time delays due to variable transfer time and focusing. We tracked the outline of the animal for all pictures and saw no significant motion over the course of the experiment. In the optimized setup we now can record continuously without moving the animal and record some frames before the feeding. The fly is only briefly illuminated for the picture acquisition and control flies showed no detectable bleaching during the observation time. In the literature the sensor is described very photo stable with more then 5min continuous exposure showing no detectable bleaching (see DOI: 10.1038/nature12354)
4. Usually when interfering with NAD metabolism enzymes this results in lethality. Thus, we were surprised when this nicotinamidase allele produced viable animals and showed a hearing deficit. We performed experiments where we supplemented animals with precursors and NAD directly to potentially rescue the knock out phenotype but saw no rescue. Data was omitted due to space constrictions. We can also not exclude that some other enzyme might be able to metabolize NAM. Nicotinamidase is astonishingly strongly expressed in the antenna but not in the rest of the body. However, if it would be an energy phenotype one would not expect strong transient reduction in amplification when feeding NAM to wildtype flies, which rather hints for a regulatory function then a indirect effect by energy production.

Behavioural experiments like climbing assays are difficult as chordotonal neurons are required for gravity sensing and flies lose anti-gravitaxis behaviour with the loss of chordotonal function. Additionally, proprioception could be affected as well, which would result in a similar phenotype due to difficulties in moving body parts. We have data on general horizontal locomotion (DAM-assay; DOI: 10.1101/pdb.prot5518) that indicates no reduction in overall activity of nicotinamidase-KO flies compared to controls.

5. I adjusted the text and only left the term for eigenfrequency in the methods part as this term is usually used to mathematically describe oscillators.